

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Alemayehu****FIRST NAME: Hewan****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied Us conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID license)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word for Mac 2021, Zotero 5.0.88, Grammarly 1.5.65

QUIZ: A SUMMARY OF ASSESSMENT

- Turabian writes that the introduction for a thesis should have three aims. Which of the following is NOT the aim of an introduction?**
 - Put your research in the context of other research?
 - Make readers understand why they should read your report?
 - Make readers understand its importance?¹**
 - Give them a framework for understanding it?
- As a general rule if you use numerical data only occasionally, Turabian writes...**

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 104.

- Spell out numbers from one through one hundred and use a hyphen if the number has two words?**²
- Spell out numbers one through ten and use a hyphen if the number has two words?
- Always use Arabic numerals?
- Only spell out round numbers followed by hundred, thousand, million and the likes?
3. **According to Bloomberg & Volpe the abstract should be...**
- Concise and Accurate.
- Written in the 3rd person.
- Limited to 350 words.
- All of the above.**³
4. **Quality markers of the findings chapter, per Bloomberg & Volpe includes:**
- Researcher bias.
- Clear complete and credible representation of the data.**⁴
- Study findings adjusted to fit expectations from research question.
- Effective use of graph and charts to present data.**

² Turabian et al., 318.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 68.

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, 84.

5. **Turabian writes the conclusion of a thesis should have three aims. Which of the following is NOT the aim of the conclusion?**
- Leave the readers with a clear idea of your claim?
 - Make readers understand its importance?
 - Suggest further research?
 - Give them a framework for understanding it?**⁵
6. **When reading for an essay, Cleenewerck & Gulma write, “to read with a purpose,” this includes asking oneself:**
- What do I already know about the topic?
 - What do I need to read to be able to answer the essay question?
 - Can I use the material to support my topic?
 - All of the above.**⁶
7. **According to the ‘ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack’ essay writing requires which two of the following:**
- Creative thinking which encourages you to broaden your ideas?**
 - Creative thinking which encourages you to narrow the focus or scope of your ideas?

⁵ Turabian et al., 104.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 11.

- Critical thinking which encourages you to broaden your ideas?
- Critical thinking which encourages you to narrow the focus or scope of your ideas?**⁷
8. **The methodology and research chapter should accomplish all of the following except?**
- Attains the purposes outlined in the introduction's research problem and research questions?
- Misalignment between the study's key components?**⁸
- Alignment between the research approach, methodology and methods of data collection?
- Depict sufficient relevant detail so the study could be replicated?
9. **The order of elements in a reference list follows which pattern for all sources, per Turabian?**
- Author, title, date (year) of publication, other facts of publication?
- Author, date(year) of publication, other facts of publication, title.
- Author, date (year) of publication, title, other facts of publication?**⁹
- Title, Author, date (year) of publication, other facts of publication?
10. **WHO member states are grouped into six regions, each of which has a decision-making body and a regional office with a regional director. When listing them give...**

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 11.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 81.

⁹ Turabian et al.,217.

- The geographical Location?
- The regions of the United Nations?
- The names in alphabetical order by country or sea and ocean?
- The names in alphabetical order by continent or sea and ocean?**¹⁰

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *Style Guide*, 2nd ed. (WHO press, 2013), 3.

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